

Title: Bitcoin

Name: Hesham Rehman

Company: Bitxoxo Bitcoin Exchange

Introduction

The decentralized form of cryptocurrency Bitcoin is the most talked digital currency worldwide. The rapid growth has been observed since the Bitcoin is introduced among the people.

Within no time the price of bitcoin shot so high which attracted the leading exchanges to launch future contracts and multiple countries started adopting the digital currency and using as a mode of payment. This is a great achievement as well the opportunity to go digital in every form in our fast working lives.

Biography

Mr. Hesham Rehman is the self-made entrepreneur. At a very young age, he decided his goal in the finance domain. He is a former founder of web development company TechSavidha and currently the CEO & Co-founder of Bitxoxo (Bitcoin Exchange in India) at the age of 29. He pursued MBA from Amity University, India and highly qualified and expert in Computer programming.